

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE INFORMATICS TEACHERS.

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Abstract: This article reveals the essence of the concept of competence. ways to pedagogically develop professional competence in learners are shown. The content of the set of competencies, which determines the level of development of pedagogical competence that can be acquired for future teachers, is highlighted.

Key words: competence, professional competence, personal experience, technologies, practical activity, development.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, all conditions and opportunities have been created for raising young people who are active, aspiring, talented and have high spiritual and moral qualities, who have acquired modern knowledge and professions - who are the decisive force of today and tomorrow. Today, the development of science and technology requires a radical change in the requirements for education and its results. Based on this, the creation of new generation standards is an important task for pedagogues. The state education standards created until now were based on the systematic-activity approach, that is, the purpose of educational institutions was to be clarified in the way of mastering knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, it is required to define new state educational standards based on the competent-active approach aimed at self-development. Because the essence of the educational process organized in higher education is not to develop the needs and abilities of students, but to convey knowledge in an information-verbal way, to form skills and qualifications. Information acquired in such a reproductive way does not sufficiently allow the listener to develop practical experience. As a result, students are exposed to a lot of information in vain, the effectiveness of education is low and it does not correspond to the real reality. More precisely, it seems as if the student is separated from real life, and the goal is to absorb only previously collected information.

MAIN PART

In order to eliminate the above actual problems, it is considered appropriate to organize educational processes based on various new approaches. Our Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, and become happy" [1] It is not without attention that the opinions of the independent Uzbekistan are aimed at developing free thinking among the youth. Therefore, it is one of the high tasks before us teachers to organize lessons based on modern approaches based on the demands of the new era. The only way out of this problematic situation is to introduce a new, competent approach in higher education. Competent approach requires the student to acquire

knowledge and skills as a whole, not separately. In connection with this demand, in turn, the system of choosing teaching methods is also changing. The selection and practical application of teaching methods requires the improvement of competencies and functions that meet the requirements of the educational process. The only way out of this problematic situation is the introduction of a new, competent approach to family education. Competent approach requires the listener to acquire knowledge and skills as a whole, not separately. In connection with this demand, in turn, the system of choosing teaching methods is also changing. The selection and practical application of teaching methods requires the improvement of competencies and functions that meet the requirements of the educational process. The competent approach is a new pedagogical reality in terms of modernization of higher education. Within the framework of this approach, practical experience, competence and competence are considered as didactic units and the traditional three elements of education (triad)

"knowledge - skill - competence" into six units (sextet) - "knowledge - skill - competence - experience of practical activity

- competence - competence" analysis is required. First of all, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the concept of "competence". Competence (a Latin word that means to reach, to be right)

readiness of the subject to effectively implement external and internal reserves to set a goal and achieve it, in other words, it is the subject's personal ability to successfully solve problems related to a specific object of activity. It should be noted that most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" are related to professional education and professional activity..

However, since this concept has the description of innovation in connection with general secondary education, there is a special need to clarify its essence. Competence is the Latin word "Competentia", the dictionary meaning of which in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "having experience". Competence is the ability to do a job effectively, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of work, the ability to meet the requirements in the performance of specific work functions [2]. Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level [2]. L.M. Mitina understood pedagogical competence as a harmonious combination of subject knowledge, teaching methodology and didactics, pedagogical communication skills and competence, as well as methods and means of self-development, self-improvement, and self-realization [3]. He distinguished the following three constituents in the structure of pedagogical competence: active, communicative and personal. Based on the structuring of pedagogical competence proposed by L.M. Mitina, we believe that the following set of competencies is sufficient and necessary, the level of acquisition of which determines the level of development of pedagogical competence for future specialists:

functional or special competence (knowledge, skills, qualifications and individual methods of pedagogical activity);

- personal or professional competence (knowledge, skills and abilities related to professional self-improvement and self-realization);

- communicative competence (knowledge, skills and competence related to the creative implementation of pedagogical activity) Concepts of professionalism and competence have common features. It should be noted that people who fully meet the established

requirements and standards do not always become true professionals, because some do not know how to apply knowledge in practice, so such pedagogical activity remains ineffective. It is appropriate to divide professional pedagogical competencies into separate types:

- special pedagogical competence; - to have sufficient information to carry out pedagogical activity at the necessary level. In addition, the pedagogue's ability to adequately assess his professional level and determine his development as a specialist depends on this type; - social pedagogical competence;

- the level of social competence determines the pedagogue's ability to effectively build relationships with colleagues, plan joint actions. Effective communication skills, pedagogical culture and responsibility for work results;

- all these are included in the concept of social pedagogical competence; - personal pedagogical competence; - this is the ability to rationally organize pedagogical work, time management, striving for personal growth are its main components [4-30]. Workers with a high level of personal pedagogical competence are less prone to burnout, able to work under time pressure.

TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY QUALITIES	
1	Formation of students' motivation
2	The ability to plan, evaluate, and establish feedback on the educational process
3	Knowledge of information and communication technologies
4	Work on yourself
5	Having knowledge of pedagogy and psychology
6	Perfect knowledge of his subject
7	Bringing innovation to the educational environment

Professional competence can include competence in professional activities, competence in professional communication, competence of a specialist in being able to demonstrate his profession. After understanding what competence is, it is not difficult to determine its levels. We can offer the following algorithm for creating a competency model: Step 1: Develop a job description. At this stage, it is important to clearly state the types of competencies required for the position. Step 2 is to determine the rate of verification. It depends on the specific characteristics of the educational institution and personnel turnover. Step 3 is to approve the procedure for conducting the test or examination on a comparative basis for each position. Step 4 Pass the test or exam. Step 5 is to analyze the data and bring it into the system. Making a decision on the results of the 6th stage assessment: sending to further study, transfer to another position, dismissal. Making a final analysis of the competence and performance evaluation of the educational institution during the reporting period of the 7th stage. Step 8: Complete risk and barrier case study development. A.A. Derkach defines competence in professional communication as - communicative competence (the ability to communicate with colleagues), - social-perceptive competence (the ability to perceive and evaluate other people), differential and psychological competence (the ability to distinguish individual psychological differences between people), - diagnostic competence (the ability to learn the characteristics of other people), - moral competence (compliance with the norms of etiquette required by this profession), - empathic competence (the ability to empathize with members of the community, understand them correctly, and other components are shown separately.

The structure of the characteristics of the specialist's socio-perceptive competence: - accuracy of perception, understanding and assessment of other people; - the ability to establish a systematic relationship with social subjects; - being able to adequately model the behavior and characteristics of the perceived person; - to be able to use various criteria in the process of interpersonal evaluation, etc. In order to form professional competence in future specialists, first of all, attention should be paid to the development of the characteristic of observation, that is, to the development of perceptive, cognitive, reflexive, empathic, motivational and prognostic aspects. In order to acquire socio-perceptive competence in the process of pedagogical activity and communication, the specialist must have humaneness, social-reflexive, knowledge and skills, a positive professional "I" image, some personal qualities (intellect, will, empathy, observation, kindness, emotional tolerance etc.) it is advisable to engage in training related to the formation of Pedagogical-psychological training-seminar, work game, master class and involvement in various practical exercises, increasing the role of professional practice, creating favorable conditions for each student to demonstrate his pedagogical activity and skills, it is possible to form socio-perceptive competence in him. . For this, it is necessary not only to master the knowledge, skills and abilities related to this field, but also to master the technique of establishing communication with people, to develop the motivational field, to increase psychological knowledge, and to psychologically prepare for professional activity.

Competency assessment criteria.

Kompetentlikning tarkibiy qismlar	Kompetentlikni baholash mezonlari
1. Tayyorgarlik	Maxsus xususiyatlar, axborotni qabul qilish va qayta ishlash xususiyatlari, o'rganish qobiliyati, tipologik xususiyatlar va boshqalar
2. Bilim	Kompetentlik, stereotiplar, bilim, kompetentlik bilan bog'liq bo'lgan o'rganishning ustunligi haqidagi tasavvurning mavjudligi
3. Tajriba	Kompetentlikka yaqin yoki aynan unga mos keladigan masala va topshiriqlarni bajarish
4. Munosabat	Kompetentlikni amalga oshirish yoki faoliyat kompetentligi bilan bog'liq holda o'ziga va boshqalarga nisbatan munosabatlarning shakllanishi
5. Muntazamlilik	Kompetentlikka bog'liq amallarga «turtki»larni nazorat qilish qobiliyati, matonat, qat'iyat, sabrlik, kompetentlikni amalga oshirish bilan bog'liq maqsadga erishishdagi to'siqlarni zabt etishga tayyorgarlik

The level of readiness to demonstrate competence can be determined according to the following criteria: the idea of self-development and self-expression, choosing a professional path, getting married, preparing to make decisions about having children, readiness to respond to one's own life, independently choosing a life path, in the field of profession willingness to form habits, etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that not only the direction of education to the learner, but also the teacher's psychological readiness for pedagogical activity is important in providing education and training to a person. In such cases, it is necessary to pay special attention to the level of professional competence of the teacher. The adoption of the competent approach in the educational system as the conceptual basis of educational reforms, the introduction of the competent approach to the educational system requires the implementation of serious changes in the educational goal, content, form of teaching, teaching methods, pedagogical and information technologies, control methods, and the role of the teacher and learner. In order to develop the professional competence of the teacher, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in pedagogical higher education. Higher education While certain works are being carried out in the direction of improving the state educational standard, curriculum and textbooks, although it is difficult to abandon the existing traditional content, it will be necessary to further clarify the content of education.

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